

Original Article

Blunt abdominal injury and damage of organs and its prognosis : A six-month survey in the crisis section of a tertiary medical care hospital

Mariam Malik¹, Usman Baig², Adnan Rashid³, Khalid Javed⁴, Hira Khalid⁵, Khalid Rehman Yousaf²

¹Department of Radiology, Shifa Hospital, Islamabad.

²Department of Radiology, Omar Hospital, Lahore.

³Department of Radiology, Sargodha Medical College, Sargodha

⁴Department of Interventional Radiology, SKMCH, Lahore

⁵Department of Radiology, Indus Hospital, Lahore

*Corresponding Author: Mariam Malik, Radiologist, Department of Radiology, Shifa Hospital, Islamabad. Email: mariammalik6429@gmail.com

Received: June 15, 2021; Revised: July 21, 2021; Accepted: Aug 5, 2021; Published: Sep 15, 2021

How to cite: Malik M, Baig U, Rashid A, Javed K, Khalid H, Yousaf KR. Blunt abdominal injury and damage of organs and its prognosis : A six-month survey in the crisis section of a tertiary medical care hospital. MedERA- Journal of CMH LMC and IOD. 2021;3(1).

ABSTRACT

Background: Trauma injury is the main source of demise in the young population and forces enormous expense on the health system. Because of high incidence of trauma injury and its related mortality in developing nations, it is by all accounts important to consider epidemiology and extent of the harm brought about by blunt abdominal trauma and extent of associated visceral injuries and their prognosis. **Methodology:** The patients presenting with blunt abdominal trauma who came to the Emergency department of Services Hospital in Lahore, Pakistan, from August 2014 till February 2015 were registered. The data for each patient was collected separately by a pre-designed questionnaire. The patients were individually followed up for prognosis. The data were analyzed by Statistical Package Software version 21. **Results:** A total of 117 patients came to the emergency department with blunt abdominal injury. The age bracket most encountered was 21-40 years and 83% of them were male. Organ damage was observed in 23(19%) of the cases. Amongst those with visceral damage, the most injured organs were liver and spleen (36%), followed by gut perforation(29%) , 6% each with urinary bladder rupture ,mesenteric tears and biliary tract injury **Conclusion:** Blunt damage in abdomen was observed more in men. The most affected age group was 21-40 years. Significant organ damage was seen in 19% of patients presenting in the emergency. The commonest cause of blunt trauma was a road traffic accident. Spleen and liver were the most frequently involved injured organs. Out of all cases with blunt injury of abdomen, 80% were cured without any adverse outcome.

Key words: Blunt Abdominal Trauma, Organ Damage, Cross-sectional Study

Introduction

There has been a worldwide rise in deaths accountable to trauma, making it the second most common cause of financial burden in hospitals. The

WHO in the next five years predicts trauma to be the first or second principal reason of loss of productive years.¹

Rapid stopping or speeding up Road traffic accidents owing to over speeding is the most frequent cause of blunt abdominal trauma accounting for 75% of all injuries.^{2,3} On laparotomy ,intrapertitoneal or retroperitoneal bleed is the most found fatal injury. Most trauma deaths tend to occur at the scene or in the first hour after trauma and are estimated to be up to 50% of all trauma deaths. Most lives are lost through delay in appropriate treatment.⁴⁻⁶

Most commonly injured solid organ is spleen followed by the liver and kidney. Hollow viscus injury may occur which may cause peritoneal irritation due to discharge of luminal contents e.g., faecal matter, urine, bile, food particles into the peritoneal cavity.⁷⁻⁸

Motorcycles are a cheap mean of transportation and are considered a foremost cause of blunt abdominal trauma accounting for 62%.⁹ According to Uganda trauma registry, Road traffic accidents represented 44% of all injuries recorded in the first half of 2010¹⁰ and at Mulago National Referral Hospital¹¹ and in East & central Africa¹² Emergency team is currently faced by a challenge of evaluating trauma patients.¹³ Inability to control massive bleeding is accountable for over 50% of trauma related deaths.¹⁴⁻¹⁶ Aggressive management may lead to non-therapeutic laparotomy with 16% negative laparotomy rate. There is a 16% chance of having operative management for those patients who are not actually candidates of laparotomy.

Because of high paces of injury, grimness and mortality brought about by it in our nation state, the point of this investigation was to assess the epidemiologic causes and extent of harm associated with blunt trauma abdomen and the prognosis.

Methodology

This cross-sectional observational cohort study was conducted from August 2014 to February 2015. This study was done in the Emergency department of Services Hospital, Lahore, Pakistan. All the patients above 18 years of age with suspected blunt abdominal trauma presenting in the emergency with bruises, abdominal tenderness or fractures were included in the study. Exclusion criteria was

presence of subcutaneous emphysema, with penetrating injuries, known ascites , pregnancy, morbid obesity and skull and spine injuries were not included. Study variables recorded included SSORTT score, age, sex and mechanism of injury and need for laparotomy and outcomes of non-operative management (Live/died). The patients who met the selection criteria had their vitals assessed and recorded on a questionnaire. They subsequently had abdominal scan using a portable machine. These patients were admitted and followed up for 3 days to see how many of them underwent laparotomy. Data were gathered in proformas with information relevant to the study. Data was stored and exported to SPSS 21 for analysis. For measurable data, mean ± standard deviation (SD) was used while qualitative data was assessed by using frequencies and percentages.

Results

117 patients with clinical doubt of blunt abdominal trauma for a period of six months from 16th August 2014 to 16th February 2015 in the Emergency Department of Services Hospital, Lahore were included and reviewed in this study. Study profile is shown in Figure 1.

Most of our patients were of 21-40 years of age accounting for 77%. There were 10 cases in the age group 10-20(9%) and 17 in the age bracket 41-50(14%). A total of 97 males (83%) and 20 females (17%) were enrolled. Male: Female ratio was 5:1. Road accident in the traffic was the major cause of injury in our study accounting for 69%. This was

followed by fall (23%), fight (6%) and others (2%). Among RTAs, accidents caused by motorcycle accounted for 62% of injuries. (Table 1)

Table 1: Baseline Characteristics and Mechanism of Injury

Characteristics	Number	Percentage
Age groups		
10-20	1	9
21-40	90	77
41-50	17	14
Gender		
Male	97	83
Female	20	17
Mechanism of injury		
Road traffic crash	80	69
Fall	27	23
Fight	7	6
Others	3	2

Focused Assessment with Sonogram in Shock (FAST), CT scan, diagnostic lavage of peritoneum(DPL) achieved by emergency and surgery consultants. Table 2 shows the frequency and type of organ damage observed. Massive hemoperitoneum with solid organ damage were the communal outcomes at laparotomy with liver tear (35%) being the commonest solid organ hurt followed by splenic tears. 5 (29%)cases of gut punctures, 1(6%) had urinary bladder breach, 1(6%) with mesenteric tears and 1(6%) with biliary tract injury.

Table 2: Highlights outcome of laparotomy patients.

Therapeutic laparotomy finding	Number of cases	Percentage (%)
Grade 4/ grade 5 injury	8	36
Massive hemoperitoneum	6	27
Gut perforation	5	23
Mesenteric tears	1	5
Bladder injuries	1	5

Biliary tract injury	1	5
Non-therapeutic laparotomy		
Retroperitoneal hematoma	1	5
Grade 2 solid organ injury	1	5

Among laparotomy patients 36% had grade 4 or 5 solid organ injury followed by massive hemoperitoneum (27%). Out of 117 patients there were 22 laparotomies and 95 patients had non operative management. Two patients expired during the course of our study out of which one with retroperitoneal hematoma and the other with massive hemoperitoneum and pancreatic head transection. This study shows the laparotomy rate of 14% and the mortality rate was 2%.

Discussion

The current study was designed to evaluate the epidemiologic and analytical features of blunt damage to abdomen and its magnitude in patients coming to the emergency department of Services Hospital Lahore. In this study, amongst the 117 cases with trauma abdomen, 97 cases (83%) were males. In parallel studies, blunted abdominal trauma was stated to be more in men.¹⁷⁻²⁰ This is probably due to the fact the men are more in outdoor activity.

In our study, the range of age was from 10-50 years. The maximum recurrent age was 20-40 years, average age was 34.15 ± 1.6 years. In comparative investigations, the mainstream of cases with blunt abdominal trauma was in the 3rd era of their lives.^{17,18}

Economic harms triggered by this trauma is not solely connected to hospital costs, commercial losses caused by infirmity, joblessness, cost of decrease in efficiency, destruction to automobiles, collected with the damage of life and infirmity admissions executes massive prices on society.⁵

The utmost common mechanism calculated in most studies and the current study of blunt trauma was a road traffic accident.^{19,20,22-26}

In this survey from 117 cases with abdominal trauma, 95 cases (81%) had no injury to any organ. Spleen and liver were alike the most bruised organs. Early management of patients is an essential feature in determining forecast for surgical or nonsurgical management.²⁷

In the existing study out of 117 patients with blunt damage, 95 cases (81%) got handling with nonsurgical procedures and 22 patients (9.6%) got surgical treatment. The growing usage of nonsurgical approaches may be due to better monitoring by imaging procedures in the emergency department.²⁷

In the present-day study, out of 117 cases, 2 (1.7%) died, and 92 patients (80%) were cured completely after surgical laparotomy while rest 13 had comorbidity. These findings are consistent with another study.²⁸

Conclusion

This survey concludes that road traffic accidents were the commonest cause of blunt abdominal trauma followed by fall and fight . On follow up, out of 117 patients , 22 of the patients underwent laparotomy while the rest were managed conservatively . In patients who underwent surgical management , different types of visceral damage were observed with liver and spleen being the most frequently involved organs followed by gut perforations , mesenteric tears bladder and biliary tract injuries. Two patients expired during the course of our study .This survey reveals a laparotomy rate of 14% and the mortality rate of 2% was observed in BAT patients at a tertiary care hospital .

Acknowledgment

We are thankful to the Emergency Department of Services Hospital Lahore for their support.

Funding

No funding of any kind was taken for this study.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

References

1. *Mock CN, Jurkovich GJ, nii-Amon-Kotei D, Arreola-Risa C, Maier RV.* Trauma mortality patterns in three nations at different economic levels: implications for global trauma system development. *J.Trauma.* 1998 May; 44:discussion 812-4.
2. *Davis JJ, Cohn I, Nance FC.* Diagnosis and management of blunt abdominal trauma. *Ann Surg.* 1976 Jun;183(6):672-8.
3. *Wilson WC, Grande CM, Hoyt DB.* Trauma Critical Care volume 1. p. 28. 1stEd.NewYolk, Informa healthcare .Informa Healthcare USA, Inc.2007.
4. *Matovu I.* Abdominal injuries in Paediatrics as seen in Mulago Hospital.(1978) Dissertation for Masters of Medicine Degree in Surgery of Makerere University;
5. *Moylan JA, Detmer DE, Rose J.* Evaluation of the quality of hospital Care trauma. *J of Trauma.* 1976 16(7):517-23. 1976 Jul; 16(7):517-23.
6. *Birabwa-Male D.* Abdominal injuries in Mulago hospital.Dissertation for Masters of Medicine 1989; Makerere University. Kampala1989.
7. *Odero W, Garner P, Zwi A.* A comprehensive review of epidemiologic studies.Road Traffic Injuries in developing countries. *Trop Med Intl Hlth.* 1997.
8. *Ajiko MM.* Outcome of blunt abdominal trauma in Mulago hospital. Kampala: Dissertation for Masters of Medicine Degree in Surgery of Makerere University; 2006.
9. *P. Chalya, J. B. Mabula, R. M. Dass et al.,* "Injury characteristics and outcome of road traffic crash victims at Bugando Medical Centre in Northwestern Tanzania," *Journal of Trauma Management & Outcomes* 2012 ; 6 (1)
10. *Tunuka C.* Extended Focused Assessment with Sonography for Trauma among blunt torso injury patients at Mulago Hospital injury patients at Mulago hospital: Dissertation for

- Masters of Medicine Degree in Surgery of Makerere University; 2012
11. Galukande M, Jombwe J, Fualal J, Gakwaya A. A Boda-boda Injuries a Health Problem and a Burden of Disease in Uganda: A Tertiary Hospital Survey. East and Central African Journal of Surgery, July-Aug, 2009; 14, (2):33-7
 12. Odimba B.F.K. Plea for use of peritoneal lavage in management of blunt abdominal trauma victims in developing countries. East and Central African Journal of Surgery 1997 Dec 3;3(2):49-52.
 13. Kirschning T, Brenner F, Stier M, Weber CF, Walcher F. Pre-hospital emergency sonography of trauma patients. Anaesthesist. 2009 Jan;58(1):51-60.
 14. Brohi K, Cohen MJ, Ganter MT, Matthay MA, Mackersie RC, Pittet JF. Acute traumatic coagulopathy. Journal of trauma. 2003;54:1127-30.
 15. MacLeod JB, Lynn M, McKenney MG, Cohn SM, Murtha M. Early coagulopathy predicts mortality in trauma The Journal of trauma. 2003;55:39-44.
 16. Marc M, Rolf L, Nedim Y, Thorsten T, Dieter R, Christian S et al. Early coagulopathy in multiple injury; An analysis from the German trauma registry on 8724 patients. Injury. 2007;38:298-304.
 17. Lankarani KB, Heydari ST, Aghabeigi MR, Moafian G, Hoseinzadeh A, Vossoughi M. The impact of environmental factors on traffic accidents in Iran. J Inj Violence Res 2014; 6(2): 64-71. DOI: 10.5249/jivr.v6i2.318
 18. Rangraz Jeddi F, Farzandipour M. Epidemiology of trauma in patients hospitalized in Naghavi Hospital, Kashan, 2000. Feyz 2002; 6 (2): 88-9.
 19. Currie RA, Watne AL, Heiskell EF, Jr., Gerwig WH, Jr. Blunt abdominal trauma. The American Journal of Surgery 107(2): 321-8. DOI: 10.1016/0002-9610(64)90275-2
 20. Mnguni MN, Muckart DJ, Madiba TE. Abdominal trauma in Durban, South Africa: factors influencing outcome. Int Surg 2012; 97(2): 161-8. DOI: 10.9738/CC84.1
 21. Salari AA, Aghili A, Pirayeh Hadad F. Demography of trauma patients due to driving accident in Yazd city. J Shahid Sadoughi Univ Med Sci 2002; 10(3Suppl): 19-26.
 22. Motie MR, Behnampour N, Alinezhad H. Epidemiology of blunt abdominal trauma in Gorgan Iran (2001-05). J Gorgan Univ Med Sci 2009; 10(4): 55-9.
 23. Mahmoodieh M, Sanei B, Moazeni Bistgani M, Tavakoli fard N. Management of blunt hepatic trauma in patients referred to Isfahan Alzahra Hospital during 1998-2008. Feyz 2011; 14 (5): 506-11
 24. Budinger JM. A patient education tool for nonoperative management of blunt abdominal trauma. J Trauma Nurs 2007; 14(1): 19-23. DOI: 10.1097/01.JTN.0000264149.80793.98
 25. Chong CF, Wang TL, Chang H. Evaluation of blunt abdominal trauma: current practice in Taiwan. Emerg Med J 2005; 22(2): 113-5. DOI: 10.1136/emj.2003.007328
 26. Giannopoulos GA, Katsoulis IE, Tzanakis NE, Patsouras PA, Digalakis MK. Non-operative management of blunt abdominal trauma. Is it safe and feasible in a district general hospital? Scand J Trauma Resusc Emerg Med 2009; 17: 22. DOI: 10.1186/1757-7241-17-22
 27. Gezen FC, Cincin TG, Oncel M, Vural S, Erdemir A, Dalkilic G, et al. Noninvasive management strategy in hemodynamically unstable patients with blunt trauma. Ulus Travma Acil Cerrahi Derg 2006;12(1): 43-50.
 28. Abri B, Shams-Vahdati S, Paknezhad S, Sepehri-Majd P, Alizadeh S. Blunt abdominal trauma and organ damage and its prognosis. J Anal Res Clin Med 2016; 4(4): 228-32. Doi: 10.15171/jarcm.2016.038

Contributions of the Authors

MA devised the plan

AB wrote the manuscript

MA did overall supervision

AD repharsed and did statistical anaysis

